

Immersive Media Retrieving Spiritual Ritual: Co-constructed Narratives of Virtual Reality, Artificial Intelligence, and Theatrical Arts

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Figure 1: The performance in Laval Virtual 2024. Photographed by Yi Chun Ko

Abstract

The research began by exploring the influence of the traditional ritual, Guan Luò Yīn, on contemporary virtual reality storytelling. Subsequently, harnessing the potential of new media, a new narrative experience system was developed. In our system, performers serve as mediators between AI and the audience, facilitating the creation of personalized narratives and adaptive soundscapes within a virtual reality environment. This triangular co-creation framework transcends the limitations of pre-written scripts, allowing for deeper explorations of inner realms and providing a more personalized storytelling experience. This project has been publicly performed in Taiwan and France over a dozen times. Future studies will concentrate on optimizing the real-time conversational narrative system and gathering extensive feedback to improve and validate its applicability and effectiveness across diverse artistic and cultural contexts.

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CCS Concepts

• Applied computing → Media arts.

Keywords

Virtual Reality, Guān Luò Yīn, Triangular Co-created Narrative, Artificial Intelligence, Immersive Theatre, Real-time Performance, Audience Participation

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1 Introduction

Guān Luò Yīn is a ritual originating in ancient primitive witchcraft areas in the southeastern part of China and Taiwan and carried forward by Taoists. It is similar to some Western rituals such as mediumship or shamanism. With the assistance of the priest, participants experience a sense of transcendence, feeling as though they have 'left' their bodies to explore the underworld, visit departed loved ones, or delve into their destinies. A pivotal step of the ritual

is blinding, symbolically severing the connection to the physical world, allowing the participants to perceive the underworld.

In the contemporary context of virtual reality in Taiwan, in online articles or academic research, the experience of Guān Luò Yin is often compared with that of virtual reality[1]. Due to their formal similarities, both require the viewer to break the visual connection of the “real world” to observe the “non-real world.”[2]

While virtual reality shares formal similarities with the ritual, the fundamental narrative approach of both remains different. Viewing virtual reality and rituals as mediums and attempting to apply Marshall McLuhan’s concept of “retrieve”[3] to analyze the analogy between virtual reality and these kinds of conventional rituals, it becomes evident that mainstream virtual reality is limited in content narrative to predetermined and replicable experiential forms. These limitations result in the analogy of virtual reality experiences being confined to superficial forms. In terms of narrative experience, virtual reality fails to inherit the uniqueness of experiences found in mediumistic rituals.

Starting from the analysis of rituals and virtual reality, a new narrative approach to virtual reality can be retrieved. This emerging media experiment may also discover new directions in the field of virtual reality. On the application side, new interactive narrative strategies can serve as a creative approach to virtual reality art, and perhaps even lead to breakthroughs in the development of virtual reality.

The research questions of the project are as follows:

- (1) Given the comparisons between the rituals and the current development of virtual reality, it is argued that the medium properties of virtual reality are not directly suitable for being regarded as a “modern spiritual ritual”. How can we retrieve the rituals through virtual reality?
- (2) How can we develop a new form of virtual reality creation by allowing virtual reality to approach the experience of the rituals? What are the differences in experience between this creative form and previous virtual reality projects?
- (3) How does the creation provide audiences and performers with a new co-creative experience?

2 Defining Statements of Virtual Reality

Walking through the mainstream of virtual reality narrative works, we often see the use of pre-written scripts and fixed plots. In these works, viewers are mostly passive audiences. However, in the spiritual ritual, participants are not only viewers but also providers of the material for the journey. Compared with the ritual, there are three states that virtual reality has scarcely touched upon: the ‘In-between Presence Journey,’ the ‘Transcendence of Consciousness,’ and the ‘Unreplicable Experience.’

2.1 In-Between Presence Journey

In the most traditional rituals, especially those involving severing the connection to the material world, the mediumship is crucial in guiding the participants through verbal instructions tailored to each individual and offering emotional support. Consequently, the ritual represents an **in-between** journey that retains a connection with the physical world.

Wearing a virtual reality headset is often likened to embarking on a journey away from the physical world, where one’s connection to reality weakens. In the mainstream work of virtual reality, the role of the medium is absent. We therefore attempt to reintroduce the ‘live mediator’ into virtual reality storytelling to retrieve the following particular characteristics of the mediumship ritual :

- (1) Accompanying audiences’ emotional and spiritual experiences.
- (2) Unreplicable experiences for audiences.

In the immersive theatre “Eve, Dance is an Unplaceable Place[4],” the dancers interacted with virtual reality artwork. They guided, danced with, and embraced the audience throughout the performance. The emotional impact of adding mediators can be verified by the feedback and the success of “Eve, Dance is Unplaceable Place.”

Regarding the second characteristic, the immersive virtual reality theatre “Cosmos Within Us[8]” creates an improvisational environment for the actors, audiences, and sound designers involved. They created improvisational theater for each live performance, providing emotional support.

By involving elements of immersive theatre, the connection between the two worlds is partly restored. In integrating the mediator into virtual reality, we continue to explore whether the mediator can go beyond following a “fixed script”, creating an experience for real **personal narrative**.

2.2 The Transcendence of Consciousness

During the conventional ritual, participants are guided to transcend their physical bodies and enter a spiritual realm. This realm exists beyond consciousness but is simultaneously constructed from the individual’s subconscious. To achieve this transcendence, audience participation is paramount, in addition to the guidance provided by performers. Examples like “#ALPHALOOP[6]” demonstrate attempts to facilitate the transcendence of consciousness within immersive media through the synthesis of images from the physical and virtual worlds. To facilitate the transcendence of consciousness for the audience in a VR experience, it is crucial to create a space that feels both private and trustworthy. The involvement of an actor can be pivotal in establishing such reliable environments in virtual reality. By doing this, we can encourage audiences to share personal narratives in a public context, thus achieving a deeper transcendence of consciousness and advancing the narrative.

2.3 Unreplicable Imagery Experience

In spiritual rituals, visuals are deeply intertwined with individuals’ life experiences, personalities, and current mental states, resulting in diverse experiences for each participant. The purpose of engaging in the ritual is to see deceased loved ones, for example, it makes the experience highly associated with personal memories. This unique feature ensures that the experience is **unreplicable** for every participant in the ritual. In the previous section, we mentioned the importance of mediators and the audience in creating personal experiences. The challenge in mainstream virtual reality is that the virtual environment is “pre-created.” One reason for this is that creators need the amount of time required to construct the virtual environment in a conventional manner. In “Real-time Stage Modeling and Visual Effects for Live Performances,”[5] a novel

live platform provides users with laser depth cameras to construct the virtual environment based on the physical world in real-time. By discussing technical development and the possibilities of **constructing virtual environments in real-time**, we can further explore how we can develop narrative techniques or perceptual frameworks to respond to these technological advancements.

With the advancement of artificial intelligence, described as the accumulation of human experiences, there is another way to construct real-time virtual environments that may be more versatile and less reliant on physical reality. LDM3D[7] is a generative model capable of producing RGB images and depth map data, which can be utilized in virtual environments. Furthermore, we can concentrate on the following state that LDM3D has not yet accomplished: It may not be enough to create a personal narrative just by “an image.” What kind of visual form we can apply in the work, emphasizing the audience’s imagery experience? We will discuss this state in the next paragraph.

3 System Design

3.1 The Triangular Co-created Narrative

Serving as a mediator between the physical world and the non-physical realm, this intermediary role is crucial for contemporary consciousness-focused work that requires interpersonal communication. Virtual reality may incorporate live performers to mediate the audiences’ shifting awareness and emotions, translating their immediate conscious perceptions into the imagery.

To achieve consciousness transcendence, narratives related to experience and consciousness must rely on audiences’ participation to closely align with their experiences and deepen their immersion. Consequently, we can no longer adhere to traditional mainstream virtual reality, whether in games or movies, with pre-written storylines. Allowing their real-time responses to generate new content can make the narrative more relevant to them and engage them in its creation.

In the realm of digital media, the vast database and computational methods of artificial intelligence allow us to extend the possibility of visual scripts and to approach nearly unreplicable experiences and narratives.

Figure 2: The architecture of the triangular co-created narrative.

We draw on the interactive characteristics and narrative methods of the ritual to bring innovative narrative approaches to virtual reality. With the involvement of artificial intelligence, the performer, and the audience, we can build a new form of narrative in virtual reality.

3.2 To Achieve the Triangular Narrative in Virtual Reality

We utilize TouchDesigner software to build the system and 3D environment, as TouchDesigner excels in real-time image processing and integrating multiple systems. Oculus Quest hardware is used as the virtual reality headset, as Oculus offers comprehensive functionality that can be integrated into TouchDesigner.

We utilize **frame-by-frame** AI-generated images as visual content for the 3D environment and visual effects. This creates a unique sense of time, simulating participants’ internal visual experiences as they explore the subconscious. The performers guide the audience to share their own stories, using the audience’s verbal descriptions as prompts to generate real-time animations that facilitate the exploration of their subconscious.

The performers act as mediators between the AI and the audience. Within this system, three performers undertake three crucial tasks:

- (1) Interacting directly with the audience to create a safe environment and guide them into the narrative.
- (2) Communicating with the AI to translate the personalized narratives co-created by the performers and the audience into the virtual environment.
- (3) Design of soundscapes tailored to different narrative scenarios during the performance.

This enhances the mysterious atmosphere of the ritual. These designs aim to provide audiences with a transcendent, beyond-reality, immersive experience, seamlessly transitioning between reality and virtuality.

Figure 3: The architecture graph of the system. The system is based on TouchDesigner.

3.3 Real-time AI-Generated Frame-by-Frame Animation

Based on the audience’s responses, the operator inputs relevant prompts and the “screen grab,” along with “image sampling” in Redream, a real-time graphics module utilizing the Stable Diffusion WebUI architecture. Redream can shorten the computation time for generating images to one-third of the original time, achieving a coherent narrative progression and resulting in **frame-by-frame** animation by incorporating the patterns from the previous frame and the current input prompts. Additionally, parameters such as “CFG scale,” “step,” and “denoising strength” are dynamically adjusted in Redream. This directly impacts the variance between successive images and computational time, thereby affecting the narrative progression and tempo of the visuals. To optimize image generation speed, the workload is divided into two computers. Image

Figure 4: The demonstrations of the AI-generated animation. The prompts of both of the images above are "a modern classroom without any people." The difference between the two comes from the previous images and the various responses of the audiences.

generation is processed in the first computer. Virtual environment establishment and the feedback effects designed for 2D images are processed on the second computer. The data is transmitted via the NDI protocol between the computers.

This real-time AI-generated animation facilitates instantaneous communication between the audience, AI, and actors, fostering the exploration of subconscious themes within the VR experience.

Figure 5: The process of how we import the AI-generated animation into the virtual environment. After the animation was created, it was mapped on the sphere as the material of the sphere. The audiences can experience 360-degree animation via the virtual headset.

4 Audience Responds

This project has undergone three phases of exhibitions with diverse audiences and settings. The participants were teachers and students familiar with VR technology. The initial showcase held in a black box on a university campus gained recognition for its ability to guide participants into their inner exploration. The second phase included a wider range of experimental samples, inviting participants with varying levels of exposure to virtual reality, cultural interests, and expertise in technology and art. Through iterative improvements, the work effectively evoked personal memories from the audience. For instance, a Russian audience member noted seeing images related to her hometown, which transported her back to her childhood, a time she rarely reminisced about. The experience also evoked some items closely tied to her memories.

In the third phase, our project was nominated for and exhibited at Laval Virtual in France, receiving accolades for its immersive and emotionally resonant experience. A notable moment occurred when a viewer shed tears during the performance. Reflecting on seeing a doll and recalling a departed friend, she described the process as healing and peaceful, enabling her to confront her sorrow comfortably.

So far, we have been experienced by approximately 60 audiences from different nationalities. Through these artistic forms, we validate the three points discussed in the first paragraph regarding co-created narratives and new forms of virtual reality. The feedback from the audience can verify the success of these forms and demonstrate their universality, independent of specific cultural contexts.

5 Conclusion

This study introduces a narrative structure in virtual reality that is co-created by artificial intelligence, audience interaction, and improvisation by performers. The focus on artificial intelligence lies primarily in the process of generating images, aimed at creating personalized exploration of the subconscious. Drawing on the concept of the Guān Luò Yīn and other similar rituals, the mediators and artificial intelligence intervene in the virtual reality, utilizing a co-creative structure to transcend the limitations of fixed scripts and explore new narratives for virtual reality. This approach allows VR to adapt the essence of traditional rituals, creating a modern spiritual experience.

Furthermore, this framework enriches the VR medium by offering similar emotional resonances among participants from diverse cultural backgrounds, providing novel insights into audience interaction and the emotional impact of immersive technologies. Compared to previous VR projects, this new form guides personalized storytelling and spiritual resonance more effectively, providing audiences with unreplacable experiences.

6 Future Development

Regarding the improvement of this system, the team is planning to conduct further experiments by participating in various exhibitions to collect comprehensive feedback from audiences of diverse backgrounds. Moreover, the team is considering visiting and collaborating with experts in the fields of artificial intelligence and theater arts. With the continuous improvement of this triangular co-created narrative structure, we believe in its potential to adapt to different improvisational scenarios and look forward to its future development in various works, exploring the possibilities of immersive experiences.

References

- [1] Chien-Lin Kuo (Ed.). 2017. VR and AR Applications in Medical Practice and Education. *The Journal of Nursing* 64, 6 (Dec. 2017).
- [2] Shin-Ju Lin. 2019. *PanX.axia Knowledge Sect Record: Interpreting Guān Luò Yīn and Yin Yang Eyes through AR and VR Technologies in Anthropological Contexts*. Retrieved January 30, 2024 from <https://panx.asia/archives/60589>
- [3] Marshall McLuhan. 1964. *Understanding media: the extensions of man* (1st. ed.). McGraw-Hill, New York, NY.
- [4] Margherita Bergamo Meneghini. 2019. Performance" Eve, dance is an unplaceable place". In *Games, Entertainment, Media Conference (GEM)*.
- [5] Taehyun Rhee, Andrew Chalmers, Faisal Zaman, Anna Stangnes, and Vic Roberts. 2023. Real-time Stage Modelling and Visual Effects for Live Performances. In *ACM SIGGRAPH 2023 Real-Time Live!* (Los Angeles, CA, USA) (*SIGGRAPH '23*). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 8, 2 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3588430.3597245>
- [6] Adelin Schweitzer. 2018. #ALPHALOOP Project 2018. Video. Retrieved April 28, 2024 from <https://vimeo.com/298684164>
- [7] Gabriela Ben Melech Stan, Diana Wofk, Scottie Fox, Alex Redden, Will Saxton, Jean Yu, Estelle Aflalo, Shao-Yen Tseng, Fabio Nonato, Matthias Muller, et al. 2023. Ldm3d: Latent diffusion model for 3d. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.10853* (2023).
- [8] Satore Studio. 2019. *COSMOS WITHIN US*. Retrieved June 28, 2024 from https://satoresstudio.com/portfolio_page/cosmos-within-us/